

RED LIST OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY (PLANTS)

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

Dataset provides the most complete list of rare and some endemic plant species of transboundary territory of the Altai Mountainous Country (AMC) within Russia, Kazakhstan, China and Mongolia. The AMC's borders are defined according to 19 botanical and geographical areas revealed by R. V. Kamelin in the first volume of "Flora Altaica" (Flora Altaica, V. 1, 2005. The team of authors (Ed.) R.V. Kamelyn, Barnaul, 340 p.). The AMC polygon (GeoJSON) for the required taxon research is available in the section "AMC Map" of the project "Flora Altaica" on the website (<http://altaiflora.asu.ru> > AMC Map). GeoJSON polygon can be implemented in "Location" item of "Occurrence" section of GBIF.

Geographic scope

Dataset provides the most complete list of rare and some endemic plant species of transboundary territory of the Altai Mountainous Country (AMC) within Russia, Kazakhstan, China and Mongolia.

Bibliography

1. Shibanova A.A., Zholnerova E.A., Zaikov V.F., Sinitsyna T.A., Shmakov A.I., Vaganov A.V. Principles of the online Red Data Book development using biodiversity datasets: the Altai Mountain Country case. *Acta Biologica Sibirica*, 2022, V. 8: 583–594.
2. Vaganov A.V., Shmakov A.I., Smirnov S.V., Usik N.A., Shibanova A.A., Kechaykin A.A., Kosachev P.A., Kopytina T.M., Zholnerova E.A., Medvedeva K.E., Zaikov V.F., Sinitsyna T.A., Shalimov A.P., Antonyuk E.V., Gudkova P.D., Dmitriev D.A., Batkin A.A., Kasatkin D.E., Belkin D.L. Virtual Herbarium ALTB: collection of vascular plants of the Altai Mountain Country / *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 2021, 9: e67616.
3. Vaganov AV, Shmakov AI, Gudkova PD. 2019. Global data on phytodiversity of the Altai mountain country, presented in the world's scientific depositories. *Problems of Botany of South Siberia and Mongolia. Proceedings of 18th International Scientific-Practical Conference (20–23 May 2019, Barnaul): 222–227. (In Russian).*

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